

MEDIATIZED EU - Mediatized Discourses on Europeanization and Their Representations in Public Perceptions

Research Summaries: Media Analysis

This series of summaries presents the results of different phases of research of MEDIATIZED EU, grouping all seven case-studies. The present issue summarises the results of media analysis.

BELGIUM

The Media Analysis Report aims to give a detailed examination of pro- and anti-European Union (EU) discourses, focusing particularly on identity and pragmatic narratives expressed across the Belgian media. It examines a selection of Belgian media discourses from August 2021 to March 2022, including five major events chosen for analysis, namely the Russian invasion of Ukraine, the COVID-19 vaccination policy and protests, EU budgets 2021-2022, and the Belarus border and migration crisis. These events received broad coverage across a wide range of Belgian media outlets, ranging from news and online news sources to television and print media. The report specifically includes discourses attempting to foster or hamper the European project and/or Europeanisation with a critical focus on understanding the many existing, new, and different discourses that are portrayed across such media outlets. It provides a detailed analysis to delve into the multitude of media interests and discursive layers, acknowledging their subjective framing, power dynamics, and untold relations. This approach enables a deeper socio-contextual examination of the power structures and interests embedded within the examined media sources in Belgium. Representations of 'Europeanisation' and pro-EU and anti-EU dominant discourses were preliminarily examined to understand the framing of 'identitarian' and 'pragmatic' discourses across the Belgian media, as well as through polls, studies, reports, and other existing academic and other literature in this specific field.

Belgium stands out among EU and non-EU partners due to its federalised and bilingual media system, governed by distinct funding, laws, and culture. This necessitated a meticulous selection process based on factors such as popularity, audience/readership, editorial stance (pro and

anti-EU), linguistic representation (Flemish and Walloon), and the inclusion of both traditional and online platforms. Notably, RTBF (Radio-Télévision Belge de la Communauté Française) was selected as a prominent news source in the Wallonia and Brussels regions, drawing significant viewership for its news-related content in Walloon French. VRT (Vlaamse Radio- en Televisieomroeporganisatie) was chosen as its Flemish equivalent. In the realm of mainstream commercial newspapers, De Standaard, a Flemish "intellectual" publication that delivers daily news, events, and analysis and has widespread readership in Flanders and Brussels, was included. Le Soir, its Francophone equivalent, was also selected. Among online news publications, Doorbraak, a right-leaning outlet, was chosen, and Medor, a Francophone online outlet contributing to the diverse media landscape in Belgium, was also included in the analysis. Both quantitative and qualitative content analyses were conducted to examine the data collected from the aforementioned media outlets mentioned, followed by a comprehensive critical discourse analysis.

The study's main actors include journalists as the most dominant across all Belgian media outlets, with the EU following closely behind. Academia and experts also hold significant influence, along with ruling parties and governments. Everyday citizens and foreign citizens are frequently coded as well, indicating their prominence in media discourse. Notably, the EU's dominance in media discourse varies across different outlets, being more prevalent in De Standaard, Le Soir, and RTBF compared to VRT, Doorbraak, and Médor. This finding clearly shows how editorial (left and right) and online media platforms dedicate less space/frequency to EU voices. Additionally, the study highlights a reliance on academic and expert views across various media platforms, except for the right-leaning online media outlet Doorbraak, which exhibits different patterns of actor dominance.

The study reveals a significant shift in discourses within Belgian media between 2021 and 2022, particularly evident across linguistic divisions. The Belarus migration crisis and the war in Ukraine have notably impacted the transformation of these discourses, leading to the reactivation of migration discussions and influencing the Europeanisation narrative. This transformation has contributed to the polarisation observed between Flemish media outlet Doorbraak and traditional broadcasters like VRT, highlighting distinct discourses regarding EU budgets and COVID-19 coverage across linguistic lines. The war in Ukraine has also sparked discussions regarding EU membership for countries like Georgia, Ukraine, and Moldova across multiple Belgian media outlets. However, differences in coverage persist between traditional providers such as VRT and RTBF compared to right-leaning online sources like Doorbraak. Despite pro-European discourses outweighing anti-EU narratives in Belgian media, there has been a notable rise in identitarian and contra-EU rhetoric on online platforms like Doorbraak. While both pro- and anti-EU discourses are present across various events, there is a stronger inclination towards an identitarian discourse observed in Flemish media compared to Francophone media.

This research looked at both identity and pragmatic narratives across Belgian media while taking into account discourses on Europeanisation. The conclusions drawn in this report stem from a

thorough cross-comparison of both qualitative and quantitative analyses. Notably, linguistic divisions persist between Flemish and Francophone media concerning Europeanisation, where Flemish outlets tend to lean towards anti-EU and identitarian narratives. These outlets exhibit a higher frequency of coverage on topics such as COVID-19 protests and reference far-right and right-wing political parties more frequently. The impact of linguistic divisions and regional media laws is significant, particularly evident in contentious topics like COVID-19 protests, EU budgets, the migration crisis, and the Russian invasion of Ukraine. Despite an overarching pro-European discourse prevailing in Belgian media, there has been a noticeable surge in identitarian narratives, particularly pronounced in Flemish media outlets and online platforms like Doorbraak.

 ESTONIA

The Estonian society is concerned with sovereignty and identity issues and remains rather sceptical of EU involvement in national issues. While both pragmatic and identitarian discourses are represented, the identitarian discourses are more referred to by Eurosceptic outlets. Estonian media reflects first of all global or European topics that appear to be current, such as the Belarussian refugee crisis; fight against Covid-19; fight against disinformation; war in Ukraine and Brussel's support for Ukraine; and the ecological crisis and implementation of the "green deal". Some general implicit assertions seem to prevail in pro-European and anti-European discourses, such as "Estonia is a European country" (pro-European narratives) vs "European liberal values endanger Estonian culture" (anti-European narratives).

The Russophone community makes up 29.6% of the Estonian population. This research does not cover the influence of the media channels from the Russian Federation banned in Estonia since 2022, which were more popular than local media in Russian language. In general, the Russian language media is pro-European. However, several discourses which get attention in the Estonian language media are non-existent or weakly represented. The Estonian channels in Russian language have two main focuses: European security policy issues, especially those related to Russia and migration and all kinds of EU regulations.

The ethnonationalist community makes up around 20-25 percent of the population, which quite consistently supports the ideological guidelines of the Estonian Conservative People's Party (EKRE). They emphasise traditionalist, conservative and Christian values, which are typical to conservative ideologies of other Eastern-European societies like Poland and Hungary. Compared to other communities, the ethnonationalist community is strongly Eurosceptic and actively disseminates its views in alternative media. The inclusion of alternative media to this research confirms that the influence of anti-European discourses to Estonian society is much higher than would be expected from the mainstream media studies. There is also an important difference that the alternative media is free for their readers, while the majority of content in mainstream outlets (except ERR) are for pay, which makes alternative media easily accessible for the audience.

We included two special discourses on the war in Ukraine and the Belarus migration crisis. All three political communities tend to support Ukraine in their war with Russia, but the ethnonationalist community is more distant on some issues like the acceptance of Ukrainian refugees. The Russophone community remained more distant during the Belarus migration crisis, but it does not support Russian positions in the war in Ukraine.

The media analysis confirms that the majority of the Estonian population supports pro-European discourses and favours membership in the European Union. There is a strong self-identification as 'European' or Europeanness among all major interest groups, including ethnonationalist and Russophone discourses. The majority of Estonians recognises membership in the European Union as a positive alternative to the further political and economic integration with the Russian Federation, but Eurosceptic ideas can easily get support in some segments of the society. The more divergent results concern the adoption of European values as the Estonian society is concerned with sovereignty and identity issues and remains rather sceptical on the EU involvement in national issues.

 GEORGIA

This media analysis report is derived from an examination of six popular media outlets in Georgia, addressing the project's objective of scrutinising media discourses that foster or hinder the European project and Europeanisation. Therefore, the selected outlets represent both pro-European and anti-European perspectives. Initially, the focus was on media outlets known for their opinion-oriented content, but later a decision was made to include those that primarily provide neutral news summaries as well. For the analysis, we identified key events from written media and examined related TV news programmes and political talk shows. The timeline is centred around several pivotal periods, commencing from the summer of 2021, marked by the far-right groups' attack of journalists covering an anti-homophobia rally in Tbilisi. It encompasses events related to the ruling party's withdrawal from the document initiated by the Head of European Commission Charles Michel, the Georgian government's refusal to accept the EU's Macro-Financial Assistance (MFA), the information leaked in the media about the government's eavesdropping on EU diplomats and other diplomatic missions in Georgia, the local Self-Government Elections of October 2021, Russia's full-scale invasion of Ukraine in February 2022 and the Georgian government's decision to abstain from joining the EU's sanctions against Russia. This analysis captures the dynamics of media representation during the above crucial periods, providing insights into the evolving discourse on Georgia's Europeanisation within the selected media outlets.

Recent surveys indicate that television and the internet are the primary sources of information for Georgia's population, In the recent past, almost all Georgian printed media have transitioned to the online format. With the project aiming to uncover media discourses influencing or hindering

the European project, the focus includes media outlets with both pro-European and anti-European rhetoric. Given the limited presence of anti-European outlets, the weekly newspaper "Georgia and World" ("GeWorld") was chosen for its active dissemination of anti-Western/anti-European discourses, closely aligning with the Russian state-funded media. Although its online subscriber base is limited, "GeWorld" strongly echoes anti-Western messages. Conversely, "Radio Tavisupleba" (Radio Liberty), supported by the US Congress, holds an overt pro-Western/pro-European stance. The Georgian Public Broadcaster (GPB) and the online newspaper "Netgazeti" maintain a "neutral" position, summarising major events and presenting diverse opinions. Other outlets, such as "Imedi TV" (pro-governmental) and "Mtavari TV" (pro-oppositional), showcase manifest positions, influenced by their ownership or funding specifics. "Imedi" and "Mtavari" lead the ranks as the most-watched and trusted TV channels in Georgia for receiving political information. Both quantitative and qualitative content analyses have been undertaken to scrutinise the data gathered from the aforementioned media outlets, followed by a thorough critical discourse analysis.

Quantitative content analysis revealed a top-five group of actors voicing the discourses on Georgia's European integration in the selected media outlets, comprising of journalists, the ruling party (GD), pro-European opposition representatives, the EU, and NGOs. Notably, ruling party officials are particularly vocal on pro-governmental private TV "Imedi," followed by GPB. Pro-European opposition parties express their views in all outlets, except for "GeWorld", while the anti-European opposition receives the highest coverage in the latter. "Radio Tavisupleba" voices EU representatives' discourses most frequently, while pro-governmental "Imedi" TV and pro-oppositional "Mtavari" TV do so least frequently. Journalists are predominantly represented in the discourse creation and dissemination role, particularly in the case of the anti-European newspaper "GeWorld," followed by "Mtavari" TV. "GeWorld" stands out as the leading outlet referencing the opinions/attitudes of Orthodox Church representatives and far-right groups.

The predominant discourses identified in key periods have been grouped into eight discursive units and juxtaposed with counter discourses, particularly those originating from the anti-European media outlet: 1. The government's/opposition's role in Georgia's European integration; 2. Russia's role in Georgia's European integration; 3. The EU's support of human rights (a pragmatic factor); 4. The EU's financial support (a pragmatic factor); 5. Georgia's aspiration towards European integration (a pragmatic factor); 6. "I am Georgian and, therefore, I am European" (an identity factor); 7. How European is Georgia? (Both pragmatic & identity considerations are implied); 8. The EU's interference in Georgia's internal affairs (a sovereignty issue). By employing Fairclough's dialectical-relational approach, the discourses have been contextualised within the respective events that prompted their emergence, thus ensuring a comprehensive analysis of three interconnected elements of representations, identities, and relations. Qualitative content analysis, specifically utilising thematic analysis, has been applied to unveil the meanings inherent in these discourses. Furthermore, critical discourse analysis has been utilised to reveal the construction of these discourses by analysing discursive strategies and ideological schemas, drawing on the works

of Wodak and van Dijk. In a broader theoretical context, the media discourses were contextualised within the framework developed by Michel Foucault, examining the interrelation between politics and discourse.

The analysis has substantiated that the media landscape intricately mirrors the highly polarised political terrain in Georgia. Pro-governmental, pro-oppositional, pro-European, and anti-European media outlets contribute to the creation of divergent discourses regarding Georgia's European integration and Europeanisation, thereby constructing distinct versions of reality. These constructions employ various discursive strategies and ideological schemas. They operate as discursive manipulations, strategically designed to persuade the audience. The tactics employed include the dichotomy of Us vs. Them, the politics of fear, topoi, intertextuality, fabrications, code switching, local coherence, modalities, metaphors, and allegories. This nuanced examination highlights the multifaceted ways in which media outlets shape and influence public perceptions through strategic discourse construction. In all media outlets, the prevailing discourses focus on the government's or opposition's deviation from the European trajectory, accompanied by accusations of pro-Russianness. As anticipated, pro-governmental media emphasises the opposition's deviation, while pro-oppositional and other outlets highlight the government's deviation from the European path. This discourse, prevalent in all media outlets and even voiced in the pro-governmental one, becomes the dominant discourse in the context of Georgia's Europeanisation. Accusations of deviation are followed by counter-blame for pro-Russianness, portraying the EU and Russia as opposing poles symbolising progress and stagnation, respectively. This discourse sparks discussions on key pragmatic (EU's human rights support, financial aid, membership prospects) and identity (reactivation of Georgians' European identity, mental Europeanisation) considerations.

HUNGARY

This part of the project aimed to identify and analyse the media discourses related to the EU in the period between 1 July 2021 and 31 March 2022. The political landscape was turbulent at that time: the preparation for the upcoming parliamentary election due on the 3rd of April intensified government propaganda in relation to the EU and the opposition parties tried to build up a cooperative strategy between themselves to challenge the populist, nativist, and anti-EU stances of the dominant government supportive media. The media context had a large impact on discourse developments: asymmetric polarisation and high ownership concentration in addition to the state influence on the market prevail, so the independent media companies are struggling to survive. The public service media regularly disseminates government propaganda.

Relying upon the Observer media monitoring platform, we collected media items in the pre-selected media that contained EU-related keywords such as: European Union, EU, Brussels,

European Parliament, European Commission, European Council. The corpus consisted of 14424 units (articles, news, transcripts of talks). About two-thirds of the items were published in pro-government and one-third in government-critical or neutral media. Then on the basis of preliminary desk-research and test coding we pursued further selection within the corpus by using additional keywords per macro-topics that attracted public interest in the examined period. As it is known from Wodak-Meyer academic work, macro-topics enable the analysis of the relationship between the text and the social context so they can be vividly applied to establish the foundations of the discourse features.

We selected eight Hungarian media outlets, including public and private, online and print, pro-government, and opposition media. Two televisions, one public and one private (M1 and RTL) for their evening news programmes, two dailies, the pro-government Magyar Nemzet (MN) and the government critical Népszava (NSZ) with their online and print versions were considered. In addition, two popular online outlets (HVG and ORIGO) were incorporated, the first government-critical, the second pro-government. Finally, we added HÍR TV and ATV, in which political discussions were frequent. The former is pro-government, the second used to represent the liberal-critical standpoints, although recently this characterisation is questionable due to a change in ownership and in parallel a changed tone.

Populist governance and the system of electoral democracy offer themes, represent particular styles and use the paraphernalia of slogans that appeared and dominated the government discourse. Moreover, due to the general media conditions the dominance of the pro-government discourse prevailed.

The following EU-related macro-topics were in the focus of the media during the examined period: European identity and the future of Europe, migration, pandemics, disinformation, war, and sexual minorities.

It is a common feature of the analysed media that among the speakers incumbent politicians are vastly overrepresented. This connects to - and partially explains - some discourse features such as the dominance of broad themes and lack of variation in discursive logic. Politicians tend to displace experts and journalists not only in the news, but also in articles and opinion-forming reviews. The role of journalists is often reduced to animating politicians' statements.

Sovereignty is a key concept in all anti-Brussels discourses; therefore, it can be defined as a discursive frame that is present in almost all topics. Pragmatic and identity factors are inherently intertwined in every discourse, as the main interpretative framework is sovereignty irrespective of whether it evolves around pragmatic or identity aspects of the theme. According to this view the Hungarian government only tries to protect the “tradition” and “normality”, which is wanted and needed by Hungarian citizens as well as by European people all around the Union.

Two discursive blocks emerged from the dominant discourses. One is the sovereigntist block; its discourses characterise the EU image of the predominant pro-government media. The sovereigntist position in positive terms is best expressed by the phrase 'a strong Europe must be built on strong nations'. In negative terms however, the emerging sovereigntist position is infiltrated by nativism and an "Us versus Them" interpretation of the connections between Hungary and the EU – which is often identified with the West per se. "The West " is frequently characterised as already rotten, abnormal, sick, consequently only the Eastern European region can protect the European tradition. The pro-government media, when using this discourse, continuously construct and reconstruct the idea that the united opposition wants to sell the country to "the West", and would give up all traditional, Christian, Hungarian values to do so. Enforced polarisation is widely applied in the interpretation of internal politics as well. Thus internal politics is strongly built in the EU related discourse, the blame game refers to the EU and to the opposition at the same time.

The other discursive block also covers several discourses, which are best represented by the integrationist category, which accepts the need for further integration. This includes those who attribute a moral or symbolic value to the EU, who have European identity, or who see the pragmatic advantages of a liberal and managed central administration, based on proper regulatory and redistributive power.

The government media – covering roughly two-thirds of the corpus - has built up and continues a negative discourse about the EU, while the government-critical outlets provide mostly neutral or positive EU-related information. The sharp contrast between the two EU-related discursive blocks can be explained by the highly polarised nature of politics as well as the polarised media. Apparently, media-politics parallelism prevails, that is both politics and media are asymmetrically polarised with the overwhelming influence of the governing elite. While polarisation is an increasingly common feature nowadays in European politics, this asymmetric polarisation further explains the features of the discursive blocks both in terms of their size and influence and in their orientation towards the European Union. This polarisation follows from the lasting populist governance and democratic decline.

IRELAND

The media analysis is based on the examination of media discourses about the EU and the European project in key Irish print, broadcast and online media outlets. The Irish media landscape is firmly part of the Anglophone media sphere, where EU affairs overlap with those of the UK and US. Ireland has a diverse and pluralist media market with professionalised media which enjoy editorial independence and media freedom and respond to an increasingly convergent media market and audience. The analysis timeline from July 2021 to March 2022 included media

coverage referencing salient EU-related issues including the aftermath of the COVID-19 pandemic and the ongoing repercussions of Brexit. January-March 2022 saw a growing number of references to EU defence and security policy in connection with the Russian invasion of Ukraine, and a revival of discourses about EU enlargement, membership and values. Dominant EU-related discourses in the media analysis were largely pragmatic and pro-European, aligning with the elite and public sentiments on Europeanisation. There was also a significant presence of discourses that were EU-critical, though not necessarily anti-EU. Elite actors including politicians, policymakers and journalists dominated the discursive space in Irish media. There was a marginal presence of actors working to undermine the credibility of European media systems and political processes: These were predominantly activated during the Brexit period, given the context of the border between the Republic of Ireland and Northern Ireland. However, the EU was still depicted by the media as championing Ireland's interests during this time.

We analysed EU and Europeanisation coverage in seven Irish media outlets, aiming to identify the dominant pragmatic and identity discourses and the actors producing them who were quoted or reported on by media editors and reporters. Ireland is known to have a low level of political parallelism and partisanship in the news media sector, which is also becoming increasingly digitised. Therefore, we selected six media outlets that were popular and credible across print, broadcast and online, with some diversity in their ideological background. All of these were mainstream outlets, including: RTÉ (Irish public broadcaster) News, Virgin Media One (private TV station), the Irish Times (national newspaper), the Irish Independent (national newspaper), and two news websites, Breakingnews.ie and Thejournal.ie. The seventh outlet, Gript.ie, a fringe news website, was added to represent the Euro-sceptical stance less prevalent in the Irish media landscape.

We conducted a content analysis and critical discourse analysis on material covering EU and Ireland's relationship and Europeanisation, collected from July 2021 to March 2022. We focused on daily evening news bulletins for the two TV channels, analysing the news segments within each bulletin. We used the Irish Newspaper Archive for sampling print media coverage, selecting the articles that referred to EU affairs or Europeanisation. For online media outlets we examined articles that included reference to the EU or Europeanisation, excluding those without any political or policy context. The initial coding during content analysis allowed us to categorise the coverage thematically, enabling further in-depth analysis of dominant discourses and clustering these into discursive units. A total of 590 articles and/or news segments were analysed, resulting in 1,186 unique references.

The Irish media adopted a moderate, mostly politically centrist tone in their coverage of the EU-Ireland relationship, reflecting the dominant sentiment in the Irish public sphere. Unsurprisingly, pragmatic discourses dominated media coverage of EU affairs and the Ireland-EU relationship, and the majority of these discourses were pro-European, echoing the 'mutual benefit' narrative. Dominant discursive units referenced salient EU-related issues including the EU's role in

managing the COVID-19 pandemic and the Brexit negotiations. The last months of the sample period were dominated by discussions of EU defence and security policy and Irish neutrality in connection with Russia's full-scale invasion of Ukraine in February 2022, as well as a revival of discourses about EU enlargement and shared EU values. There was also a significant presence of discourses that were EU-critical, though not necessarily anti-EU, legitimating concerns about the perceived ineffectiveness of some EU policies or about democratic backsliding among some EU members.

Elite voices – i.e., politicians, policymakers and journalists – dominated the discursive space across Irish media of all types, with far less representation from civil society, citizen and academic actors.

The most dominant discourse in our data set was "The supremacy of EU law over national legislation is one of the cornerstones of the EU, but it sometimes causes tensions within member states", which underscores tensions between the overall positive assessment of the EU in Irish media and concerns Ireland's own interests on the global stage. On the other hand, the Brexit-related discursive cluster showed Irish media recognised that "Brexit has severely disrupted several sectors of economy in EU member states", yet praised the EU for "handling Brexit negotiations with care and generosity, in contrast to the UK", while underscoring the Irish perception of the paramount importance of the Northern Ireland protocol and the border issue for Brexit negotiations.

The discursive cluster formed around Russia's invasion of Ukraine was more controversial. On the one hand, the discourse of solidarity – both external (solidarity with Ukraine, people displaced by war) and internal (solidarity among EU member states on a decisive response to Russian aggression) – was quite dominant and connected to the discourse of shared EU (and Irish) values. On the other hand, the media gave prominence to the revived elite debate about Irish political and military neutrality in the light of Russia's war in Ukraine, presenting a range of political actors varying in their approaches to the interpretation of the term and the way forward for Ireland in the EU. Neutrality in Ireland and the absence of a common defence policy in the EU is discussed in both pro-European and Euro Sceptical media as an issue that merits serious consideration.

The counter-discourses focused on issues of sovereignty and autonomy of member states bound by shared EU decisions, which sometimes go against national interests. The fringe anti-EU outlet Gript.ie adopted an identity-driven EU-sceptical stance, highlighting the need for Ireland to protect its own interests and guard its sovereignty. However, this counter-discourse was peripheral to the overwhelmingly Euro-optimistic or Euro-critical pragmatic discourses.

The discursive clusters around Brexit and Russia's war in Ukraine dominating our media analysis validated the solidarity discourse underpinning the 'two-way affair' of Ireland-EU relations and its key role in geopolitical decision making based on support for democratic values and peace as the common ground between Ireland and other EU members. Our analysis, following the Foucauldian

framework (1991) also revealed the dynamics of how some discourses, such as the solidarity and shared values ones, are conserved, while others, such as the discourse about Irish military neutrality, are revived by elite actors seeking to address new challenges and concerns for Irish geopolitical position in the context of its EU membership, such as the threat of Russia's attack on Ukraine (and the shared European democratic values). Even in these cases, Irish media coverage, we found, largely mirrors the dominant elite discourses, and continues to revisit the 'mutual benefit' narrative to circumscribe Ireland-EU relations, with little oxygen for counter-discourses that are overtly identity-driven or anti-EU.

PORTUGAL

In Portugal, media analysis covered news stories, interviews, editorials, opinion and feature articles and reportages issued or aired from September 1, 2021 through March 3, 2022 by outlets with the highest-ranking audiences: the privately owned newspapers *Correio da Manhã*, *Jornal de Notícias*, and *Público*, and the evening news shows of two private and one public TV channel: SIC, TVI and RTP1. These items focused on the EU and reflected significant international and regional crises and events of the period. Domestically, particularly relevant events included the effects of the COVID-19 pandemic, the adoption of Portugal's Recovery and Resilience Plan by the European Commission, and local and national Parliamentary elections, all of which involving EU topics and dynamics.

The sample's overwhelming majority of items are of an informative-type (news), with a significant element of opinion in editorials, articles, political commentaries, and so forth. Apart from journalists, editors, analysts, experts or scholars, the most frequent authors of these items come from the Portuguese Government, Presidency or Army. In newspapers, the general public or readers are also among them, contributing articles and letters. But identifying the stories' main agents and sources help explain the perspectives reproduced. They are the EU organs or representatives; other states' Government or Army officials; and in third place, the Portuguese Government or Presidency.

The subjects most often covered on TV and newspapers –in different order according to each outlet– were security and defence; foreign policy and world diplomacy; borders; fiscal, monetary and commercial practices and policies; health solutions such as vaccines; refugees and asylum seekers; social issues such as unemployment and poverty; democracy; EU funds and financial assistance. Some of these subjects are closely related, and their synthesis also reveals interesting patterns and trends of concern discussed in the Portuguese media.

Based on these results, the analysis identifies the pragmatic (e.g. economics, security and defence) and identity factors (e.g. values) mobilised in discourses about the EU and the European project in

the Portuguese media and the trends in representation of the EU and the European project. It then organises 10 main discursive units emanating from the outlets, which are often divergent in content about Portugal's position but not regarding the importance of its integration into the EU. They are the following:

- 1) Portugal must adapt to the EU;
- 2) Portugal is peripheralized in the EU;
- 3) Portugal is well integrated in the EU;
- 4) The EU imposes norms and policies on members to provide coherence to the EU project;
- 5) The EU contributes to national development;
- 6) The EU is fragmented or troubled;
- 7) The EU must adapt or reform;
- 8) The EU is solidary and helps Portugal when it needs;
- 9) The EU is democratic and promotes democracy;
- 10) The EU and NATO, together, keep the Euro-Atlantic safe from new threats and challenges.

Discussion about the EU in Portugal is not polarised in pro-EU and anti-EU discourses, as in other cases. Instead, the debate about Portugal's integration in the EU and its "Europeanisation" is rather characterised by different perspectives of advantages and disadvantages, benefits or burdens, opportunities and costs, and of Portugal's peripheral / central position in this process. Although no overtly anti-EU stances were found, there are critical propositions about the EU's need to change in some key conjunctural and structural respects – e.g., to adopt coherent and coordinated policies in key areas or, as mainly argued by leftist actors, to strengthen its social role in order to avoid neoliberalisation or securitising migration flows, and thus promote inclusive development and actual social solidarity. The main proposition in these criticisms is not that Portugal should leave but contribute to the EU's change.

In all, the EU is depicted in an extremely positive way, particularly by means of news stories and with a primordial focus on economic issues. This positive representation is quite stable and conveys an understanding of a consensual perspective. It is built, above all, around pragmatic elements and from a logic of conservation and reactivation of discourses across time, as conceptualised in the Foucauldian framework of analysis. This building logic has secured a feeling of continuity and pervasiveness concerning positive perceptions on the EU. The apparent consensus emanating from dominant discourses is therefore that the EU is good for Portugal and having the EU, even if imperfect, is better than having no EU, concerning all areas in society in terms of current well-being, capacity to deal with crisis and challenges ahead. Moreover, the EU is deemed a natural place for Portugal in terms of political and axiological options and identity.

Europeanisation in Spain has been marked by a strong political pro-European consensus from the moment Spain first applied for membership in the European Community (EC) until today. Previous empirical studies demonstrate that the identification of Spanish elites with the European project is stronger than the identification of the Spanish public with it. Among Spanish elites, political elites show the highest levels of identification with the EU, followed by media and union elites.

This media analysis report is derived from an examination of six popular media outlets in Spain focusing on the project's objective of analysing how media discourses can foster or hinder the European integration project and Europeanisation. The selected outlets for our study represent the Spanish media landscape based on key criteria, as would be explained in the subsequent section. A final sample of 540 news items collected between July 2021 to March 2022 and was selected for analysis combining quantitative and qualitative methodologies.

The Spanish media is characterised by a high level of political parallelism. This entails that the polarised structure of the political map is reflected in the structure of the media. However, in the absence of political polarisation on European integration among Spanish political elites, such polarisation does not exist in the media.

For the purpose of media analysis, we selected six representative media outlets based on the following criteria: (a) ownership (public/private), in order to represent both models that exist in the Spanish media landscape; (b) format (traditional/digital) to guarantee the representation of the digital media market; (c) editorial line (conservative/liberal) by selecting media outlets from the most conservative to the most liberal editorial lines; and (d) type of media (TV stations and newspapers), for representing the media with the largest readership and viewership in Spain.

The chosen outlets were: ABC, Antena 3, El Confidencial, edDiario.es, El País and RTVE. The research team used the Twitter accounts of all the selected media to proceed with a massive data download. Although the analysis focuses on six media outlets, we collected data from 12 Twitter accounts to cover the general accounts of these outlets (e.g., @abc_es) as well as their international accounts (e.g., @abc_mundo) or from news programmes in the case of TV (e.g., @antena3inter).

Quantitative content analysis revealed that the top-three groups of actors identified in terms of their presence in media items covering the EU are: EU representatives, foreign governments, and Spain's national government and regional governments. Less dominant actors include representatives of other international organisations, experts, civil society, oppositional parties, citizens and journalists.

After selecting the final sample of media items, we carried out content analysis. We established categories and codes to identify key topics discussed when covering the EU issues, such as, human rights, security, economy, migration, energy, COVID-19, Ukraine, and Brexit. After completing the

thematic analysis, we identified the major discourses that emerged in relation to the discussed themes. Furthermore, critical discourse analysis has been utilised to uncover communicative strategies, hidden meanings, and connections in the sample. In a broader theoretical context, the media discourses were contextualised within the framework developed by Michel Foucault, focusing on the sayable, conservation, memory, reactivation and appropriation.

The dominant discourses identified throughout the research period have been grouped into eight discursive units that included adjacent discourses and counter discourses to each dominant discourse. The dominant discourses were: 1. The reluctance of the EU to assume its role in managing the energy crisis is creating a gap between the EU and Spain; 2. Blocking recovery funds to induce compliance with human rights is necessary because the EU is a space of values and human rights; 3. The EU needs to strengthen its geopolitical role and common security; 4. The EU needs to harmonise its policies as in the management of the migration crisis; 5. The adoption of the Next Generation funds marks a turning point in the European project; 6. Brexit was a myopic move and a mistake for the UK; 7. The EU management of the COVID-19 crisis was a success story; and 8. The EU showed unprecedented unity and decisiveness in responding to the outbreak of the Ukraine crisis.

The media analysis reinforces existing scholarship on Europeanisation in Spain, which is marked by a high support for the EU among political and media elites, even in times of crisis. This is evident in the major discourses identified that show a strong pro-European sentiment even if some criticism is embedded in them. Counter discourses showing any form of Euroscepticism remained very marginal. Still, it is important to remember that the economic crisis of 2008 in particular had negative consequences for support of the EU in Spain. However, the discourses identified in our research demonstrate that the adoption of the Next Generations funds and other policies were viewed as a corrective measure, or as a window of opportunity for the future of European integration. Media discourses constantly compared the importance of the recovery funds with the austerity measures adopted in the midst of the economic crisis. Intertextuality was very evident in discourses on the Next Generation funds.

Our research also demonstrates that Spain is pursuing a leadership role in the EU, which can also be contrasted to its weaker position during the economic crisis. This role could be inferred from Spain's successful advocacy of the Iberian exception in energy and leading vaccination rates in Europe. To assert Spain's leadership role, the "us v. them" strategy was deployed in two ways. First, it was deployed against dominant countries, mainly Germany, in the EU to criticise their lack of enthusiasm for certain fiscal policies. This strategy aimed at challenging the North/South divide. It was also used against ultra-right-wing governments from Eastern Europe but this time to enhance the position of Spain in the EU as the representative of true European values.

**For more information on the project and on our results, visit us at
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